

**“A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF INTRA OPERATIVE PERITONEAL
LAVAGE WITH NORMAL SALINE AND METRONIDAZOLE SOLUTION
VERSUS PLAIN NORMAL SALINE IN CASES OF PERITONITIS”**

By

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Dissertation submitted to B. L. D. E. University, Bijapur.

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

MASTER OF SURGERY

IN

GENERAL SURGERY

Under the Guidance of

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

C	-	Cervical
COLA	-	Covered Laparostomy
CBC	-	Complete Blood Cell
IV	-	Intra Venous
IPPV	-	Intermittent Positive Pressure Ventilation
IOPL	-	Intra Operative Peritoneal Lavage
L	-	Lumbar
OPA	-	Open Abdomen
PR	-	Planned Relaparotomy
S	-	Sacral
STAR	-	Staged Abdominal Repair
T	-	Thoracic

ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION

Peritonitis is a common emergency encountered. Despite a better understanding of peritonitis it remains a potentially fatal. Intraoperative peritoneal lavage significantly reduces endotoxin levels in the peritoneal fluid, reduces the occurrence of secondary foci by its physiologic debridement of fibrin, blood, bacteria and debris of the abdominal cavity. Antibiotics may be combined with the lavage to further reduce bacterial survival.

AIMS & OBJECTIVES

The aim of study is to determine whether intra operative peritoneal lavage with metronidazole and normal saline solution has better outcome than plain normal saline lavage in cases of peritonitis and compare the outcome in terms of surgical site infections, intra-abdominal abscess, sepsis and hospital stay in both groups.

MATERIAL & METHODS

All patients admitted in BLDEU'S Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Bijapur from October 2012 to May 2014 with peritonitis and underwent laparotomy were taken as subjects for study. A total of 76 patients were studied, who were randomly divided into two groups size of 38 patients each.

RESULTS & CONCLUSION

There was reduction in incidence of wound infection in metronidazole lavage group by 15.79%, intraabdominal abscess reduction by 5.26% and reduction in sepsis by 17.1%. Mean hospital stay was lesser in metronidazole lavage group by 1.24 days. Mortality was increased by 2.63% in metronidazole lavage group. The increased mortality in metronidazole lavage group may be due to selection bias. However none of the findings were found to be statistically significant. There is small improvement in outcome when metronidazole lavage is used in peritonitis patients, but not up to significant levels. Further studies are needed with larger sample size to assess the statistical significance of the findings.

CONTENTS

SL.NO	CHAPTER	PAGE NO
1.	INTRODUCTION	1
2.	AIMS & OBJECTIVES	3
3.	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	4
4.	MATERIALS AND METHODS	36
5.	RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS	39
6.	DISCUSSION	47
7.	CONCLUSION	52
8.	SUMMARY	53
9.	BIBLIOGRAPHY	54
10.	ANNEXURES	
	Annexure I – Ethical Clearance	60
	Annexure II- Clinical Photographs	61
	Annexure III - Informed Consent	64
	Annexure IV - Case Performa	68
	Annexure V - Key to Master Chart & Master Chart	72

LIST OF TABLES

SL.NO	TABLES	P. NO
1.	Age Specific Distribution of Cases	39
2.	Sex Distribution of peritonitis cases	40
3.	Causes of Peritonitis	41
4.	Operative procedures performed	42
5.	Outcome in Saline lavage Group	43
6.	Outcome in Metronidazole and Normal Saline Lavage group	44
7.	Comparison of outcomes of Plain Normal Saline group versus Normal saline and Metronidazole lavage group	45
8.	Mean Hospital stay in saline lavage group and metronidazole lavage group	46
9.	Comparison of age distribution with previous studies	47
10.	Comparison of sex distribution of cases with previous studies	48
11.	Comparison of cause of peritonitis in different studies	49
12.	Comparison of outcome in different studies	50

LIST OF GRAPHS

SL.NO	FIGURES	P. No
1.	Age Specific Distribution of Cases	39
2.	Sex Distribution of peritonitis cases	40
3.	Causes of Peritonitis	41
4.	Operative procedures performed	42
5.	Outcome in Saline lavage Group	43
6.	Outcome in Metronidazole and Normal Saline Lavage group	44
7.	Comparison of outcomes of Plain Normal Saline group versus Normal saline and Metronidazole lavage group	45
8.	Mean Hospital stay in saline lavage group and metronidazole lavage group	46

INTRODUCTION

Peritonitis is a common emergency encountered by surgeons the world over. Peritonitis is defined as inflammation of serosal membrane of abdominal cavity and the organs within it. Peritonitis is caused by introduction of infection into sterile peritoneal cavity by simple or traumatic perforation of viscera or by irritation or translocation of bacteria through ischemic gut wall. It may also follow introduction of chemical irritant like gastric acid secondary to gastric perforation or following acute pancreatitis. Despite a better understanding of pathophysiology, advances in diagnosis, surgery, antimicrobial therapy and intensive care support, peritonitis remains a potentially fatal affliction.¹

Early operation, elimination of focus with appropriate antibiotic therapy and intra operative lavage are the key elements of management of peritonitis. Fluids like sterile water, warm saline, aqueous betadine and various antibiotics have been used for intra operative peritoneal lavage.

The concept of lavaging a contaminated or infected peritoneal cavity makes good sense intuitively. However, because microbes adhere to mesothelial cells, it is very difficult to wash them off the peritoneal surface. During fecal contamination of the peritoneal cavity, it has been demonstrated that bacteria that adhered to the mesothelium were resistant to intraperitoneal lavage, resulting in only transitory reductions of bacterial populations. Peritoneal irrigation with normal saline is not sufficient to eliminate all fecal contamination produced during the surgical act. With the antibiotic lavage there is topical effect of the antibiotics which could completely inhibit the growth of bacteria in the peritoneum, even when microorganisms have adhered to the mesothelial cells.²

Intra operative peritoneal lavage significantly reduces endotoxin levels in the peritoneal fluid, reduces the occurrence of secondary foci by its physiologic early debridement of fibrin, blood, bacteria and debris of the abdominal cavity.³

Lavage has also been proposed to remove proinflammatory cytokines that may enhance local inflammation. Therefore, flushing the peritoneal cavity may reduce the bacterial load, inhibit bacterial proliferation, and possibly minimize peritoneal adhesions. Antibiotics like metronidazole, gentamicin sulfate, cephalothin, lincomycin, kanamycin, doxycycline, and ampicillin have been tried.²

Some studies show that addition of antibiotics to saline does not have distinct advantage over warm saline lavage. It has been shown by experimental studies that adequate levels of antibiotics are attained in the peritoneal fluid with IV injections.⁴

Although the benefits of intraoperative peritoneal lavage are well established, not many studies have been done regarding whether addition of antibiotics like metronidazole to lavage increases its efficacy and hence this subject warrants further study.⁵

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

To determine whether intra operative peritoneal lavage with metronidazole and normal saline solution has better outcome than plain normal saline lavage in cases of peritonitis and compare the outcome in terms of :-

- a) Surgical site infections
- b) Intra abdominal abscess
- c) Sepsis and other complications
- d) Hospital stay

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HISTORICAL ASPECTS

One of the earliest mentions of peritoneum can be found in Edwin Smith Papyrus written 1700 yrs ago around the time of Egyptian god of medicine Imhotep. Breasted in his translation of above work wrote "I felt as if I had been peering through a newly revealed window, opening upon the once impenetrable gloom enveloping man's earliest endeavors to understand the world he lived in. It was as if I had watched a hand slowly raising the curtain that covered this window, and then suddenly the hand had refused to lift, the curtain further". The curtain may have meant peritoneum.

Hippocrates was the first to give the description of patient with peritonitis⁶ - hippocrates facies i.e. sick and wasted look with pointed nose, sunken temples, eyes sunken and dull, furrowed tongue, shiny skin and fear on face.⁷ He also described septic shock which is still a major challenge to surgeons today. Severe diffuse peritonitis is still a 'Giant Killer'.

Rawlison in 1727 first gave description of signs and symptoms of peritonitis and gastric ulcer. Later Smith, Travers and Elliston gave clear description of peritonitis independently in 19th century.⁸

In early 19th century the treatment of peritonitis was food abstinence, purgation, absolute rest, venesection, cold application to abdomen, opium administration etc. Later with advent of general anesthesia and asepsis, surgical techniques came into practice. McDowell performed first laparotomy for a case of infected ovarian cyst and later Mikulicz advocated laparotomy for all cases of purulent peritonitis. Intra operative peritoneal lavage was first performed by Joseph Price using sterile water.⁹

Since then different fluids have been used for peritoneal lavage like warm saline, aqueous betadine and various antibiotics and has become the standard surgical management.⁹

ANATOMY OF PERITONEUM:^{10,11,12}

Peritoneum is the largest and the most complex serous membrane in the body. Anteriorly and laterally it lines abdominal wall, posteriorly it forms boundary of retroperitoneum, inferiorly covers the extra peritoneal structures in pelvis and superiorly covers the undersurface of diaphragm thus forming a closed sac in males. In females the fallopian tubes penetrate the cavity. the peritoneum that lines the abdominal wall is called parietal peritoneum and it reflects over the viscera to form the visceral peritoneum.

The peritoneum is lined by single layer of mesothelial cells which is kept moist and smooth by serous fluid. Below the cells is the loose connective tissue layer that has rich blood and lymphatic supply, nerve endings, lymphocytes and macrophages.

PERITONEAL CAVITY^{11,12}

It is the potential space between the parietal and visceral peritoneum. It contains the peritoneal fluid (< 50 ml) that is plasma ultra filtrate rich in electrolytes, proteins and desquamated mesothelial cells.

The cavity consists of

- Greater sac i.e. the general peritoneal cavity
- Lesser sac or omental bursa which is bounded by the pancreas and kidney posteriorly, stomach anteriorly and laterally by liver and kidneys.
- Both are connected by epiploic foramen.

Fig.1 Peritoneal reflections in the abdomen (sagittal view)

GREATER OMENTUM

It is a curtain like membrane attached to greater curvature of stomach and overlying the coils of intestines. It consists of closely apposed layers of peritoneum enclosing rich network of blood vessels and lymphatics. It moves to the site of infection within the abdomen and becomes adherent to the site and seals it off. It also attracts leukocytes to the site thereby preventing spread of infection. Hence it is called 'policeman of abdomen'.

Fig 2. Peritoneal reflection in upper abdomen(coronal view)

Fig 3. Peritoneal reflection in lower abdomen (coronal view)

LESSER OMENTUM

The peritoneal layers extend from liver to lesser curvature of stomach to form to form lesser omentum.

PERITONEAL COMPARTMENTS ¹³

The peritoneal reflections and mesentric attachments divide the peritoneal cavity into different compartments - four peritoneal and three extraperitoneal spaces

The transverse mesocolon divides the peritoneal cavity into supracolic and infracolic compartments

Supracolic compartment further divided into

- right upper or right subphrenic compartment
- right lower or hepatorenal pouch of Morrison
- left upper or left subphrenic compartment
- left lower or left subhepatic compartment

Infracolic compartment further divided into - right upper and left lower compartments. The peritoneal reflections and the mesenteric attachments compartmentalize the intraperitoneal space and route, spreading exudates to sites that are often distant from the source. The transverse mesocolon divides the peritoneal cavity horizontally into an upper and a lower space. The greater omentum, extending from the transverse mesocolon and the lower border of the stomach, covers the lower peritoneal cavity.

The peritoneal cavity has several recesses into which exudates may become loculated. The most dependent recess of the peritoneal cavity in the supine position is in the pelvis. Between the rectum and bladder in men is a pouch of peritoneal cavity that extends slightly below the level of the seminal vesicles. In women, the uterus and fallopian tubes project into the pelvic recess. Between the rectum and the body of the

uterus is the pouch of Douglas, which lies above the posterior fornix of the vagina. On either side of the rectum and bladder are the pararectal and paravesical fossae. The pelvic recess is continuous with both the right and left paracolic gutters.

The phrenicocolic ligament, which fixes the splenic flexure of the colon to the diaphragm, partially bridges the junction between the left paracolic gutter and the left perihepatic space. In contrast, the right paracolic gutter is continuous with the right subhepatic space and the right subphrenic space. A posterior extension of the right subhepatic sac, Morrison's pouch, is the most dependent portion of the supine position of the right paravertebral groove and lies just above the beginning of the transverse mesocolon. The horizontal posterior reflection of the serosal surface of the liver onto the diaphragm, (the right triangular and coronary ligaments), and the vertical reflection (falciform ligaments) divide the right perihepatic space, into right subphrenic and right subhepatic spaces. The left subphrenic and subhepatic spaces communicate freely around the smaller left lobe of the liver, and it is more superiorly placed to left triangular ligament. The right and left subphrenic spaces are separated by the falciform ligament, which probably prevents the spread of pus to the opposite side and explains why only about 5 to 15% of subphrenic abscess are bilateral. The left subhepatic space is divided by the gastro-hepatic omentum into an anterior space and the lesser sac.

Abscesses within the perihepatic spaces become localized by pyogenic membranes. In the right subphrenic space, they lie anteriorly or posteriorly and in the subhepatic space, superiorly or inferiorly. Abscesses of the left perihepatic space are either in the single left subphrenic or in the lesser sac.

Because of limited communication from the lesser sac to the major cavity via foramen of Winslow, suppuration in the lesser sac lie between the stomach and

pancreas but may spread to the right and lie anterior to the right kidney and inferior to liver. After intraperitoneal injection of water soluble contrast material, selectively into various intraperitoneal spaces, Autio demonstrated that right paracolic gutter is the main communication between the upper and lower peritoneal cavities.

Fluid introduced into the right upper peritoneal space gravitates towards Morrison's pouch and then into the right subphrenic space and along the right paracolic gutter into the pelvic recess. Flow of fluid in the left upper peritoneal space is mainly into the left subphrenic space. The phrenicocolic ligament limits flow inferiorly into the left paracolic gutter. Fluid introduced into the lower peritoneal cavity first gravitates to the pelvic recess and then ascends, whether in supine or erect position, along the right paracolic gutter into the right subhepatic space, especially into Morrison's pouch and into the right subphrenic space.

Ascension of fluid from the pelvic space along the left paracolic gutter is minimal and is limited by phrenicocolic ligament. Although gravity would account for the pooling of fluid in the dependent peritoneal recesses, such as the pelvic recess, ascension of fluid from the pelvis to the subphrenic space is probably caused by hydrostatic pressure differences between the upper and lower peritoneal cavities created by diaphragmatic motion. Normal intestinal and abdominal wall motion would also account for some spread of intraperitoneal fluid.

The anterior retro-peritoneal space between the peritoneum and anterior renal fascia contain the ascending and descending colons, duodenum and pancreas. The kidneys and ureters lie within the posterior retro peritoneal (perinephric) space. The renal fascia encloses the kidneys and adrenal superiorly and laterally, but not inferiorly, favoring spread of infection in this space inferior.

Nerve supply¹⁴

The parietal peritoneum is sensitive to touch, pain, temperature and pressure. The innervations of parietal peritoneum are similar to that of overlying muscles and skin i.e. lower six thoracic and first lumbar nerves. The peritoneum lining the diaphragm is supplied by phrenic nerves centrally and peripherally by lower six thoracic nerves. The visceral peritoneum is supplied by autonomic afferent nerves supplying underlying viscera and is sensitive only to stretch.

The difference in innervations accounts for the sharp severe persistent pain with irritation of parietal peritoneum and poorly localized dull pain and nausea with visceral peritoneum irritation or inflammation.

PHYSIOLOGY OF PERITONEUM¹⁵

The peritoneum is lined by single layer of mesothelial cells supported by richly vascularised loose connective tissue.¹⁶ The surface area is extensive i.e. around 1.8 m².¹⁷ Normally < 50 ml of fluid is present within peritoneal cavity which is circulated throughout the peritoneal cavity. The fluid contains macrophages (40%), leukocytes (50%), eosinophils (10%), mast cells, proteins <3g/dl and, 300cells/mm³. The peritoneal fluid functions to act as a lubricant to facilitate peristalsis and also plays a role in defense mechanism. The fluid is absorbed into the lymphatic circulation by parietal peritoneal surface and through diaphragmatic lymphatics.¹⁸ Microorganisms, cells and other particulate matter are usually cleared by diaphragmatic lymphatics.¹⁹

The diameter of lymphatic stomata vary with stretching and contraction from 4 to 12 microns.^{20,21} The negative intra thoracic pressure during inspiration facilitate movement of peritoneal fluid into central circulation via thoracic lymphatic channels and thoracic duct. Presence of inflammation can increase the patency of the stomata.²² Head up position,²³ general anaesthesia,²⁴ blockage by platelets or talc can reduce

fluid movement and thereby reduce spread of infection. Phagocytosis by peritoneal macrophages also play a role in clearance of infection.

Fig.4 : Histology of peritoneum

Fig.5 : Stomata in the diaphragmatic peritoneum

PERITONITIS^{25,26}

CLASSIFICATION

Peritonitis is organized into three divisions based upon the source and nature of microbial contamination

I. Primary Peritonitis

- A) Spontaneous peritonitis of childhood
- B) Spontaneous peritonitis of adult
- C) Peritonitis with continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis
- D) Tuberculosis peritonitis

II. Secondary Peritonitis

A) Perforation peritonitis

- a. Gastrointestinal tract perforation
- b. Pelvipertitonitis
- c. Peritonitis after translocation of bacteria

B) Postoperative peritonitis

- a. Leak of an anastomosis
- b. Leak of suture line
- c. Stump insufficiency

III. Tertiary Peritonitis

I. Primary Peritonitis:

It is defined as an infection, often monomicrobial, of the peritoneal fluid without visceral perforation.

II. Secondary Peritonitis:

It refers to peritoneal infection arising from an intra-abdominal source, majority of these episodes are the result of primary lesions of the stomach, duodenum, small intestine, colon and appendix. It is by far the most common form of peritonitis.

III. Tertiary peritonitis:

It develops following the treatment of secondary peritonitis and represents either a failure of the host inflammatory response or a superinfection.

Perforative peritonitis is defined as the end result of a disease process of trauma which extends through the muscular and serosal walls of the gastro-intestinal tract, establishing a communication between the lumen of the viscus and the surrounding body cavity and permits free egress of the luminal contents into the cavity.

ETIOLOGY

I. Perforative peritonitis:^{25,27}

Source Regions		Causes
Stomach	-	Peptic ulcer perforation Malignancy (e.g. adenocarcinoma, lymphoma, gastrointestinal stromal tumor)
Duodenum	-	Peptic ulcer perforation
Small bowel	-	Salmonella enteritis Ischemic bowel, Crohn's disease. Meckel diverticulum, intestinal tuberculosis Incarcerated hernia (internal and external) Parasitic peritonitis due to perforation by round worm

Large bowel & Appendix -	Closed loop obstruction
	Malignancy (rare)
	Ischemic bowel
	Diverticulitis
	Malignancy
	Ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease
	Appendicitis

II. Chemical (aseptic) peritonitis

Aseptic peritonitis refers to the peritoneal inflammation from substances other than bacteria. It is soon followed by bacterial colonization and sepsis. Causes include the following,

- Perforated peptic ulcer in initial stage
- Biliary peritonitis due to perforation of Gall Bladder /after open or laparoscopic Cholecystectomy due to bile leak.
- Blood in the peritoneum (e.g. a ruptured graafian follicle or following splenic injury)
- Meconium and urine may also precipitate chemical peritonitis.
- Starch used in glove powder also causes chronic granulomatous peritonitis.

III. Traumatic peritonitis

Abdominal trauma may produce acute peritonitis in following ways.

- a) Penetrating wounds of the abdomen without visceral injury provides a route for exogenous bacterial contamination.
- b) Penetration of a visceral organ causes spillage of visceral contents into the peritoneal cavity.
- c) Severe blunt trauma may disrupt intra-abdominal organs directly or indirectly through disruption of their vascular supply.

IV. Drug-induced peritonitis

Warfarin anticoagulation can cause peritoneal irritation and peritonitis through leakage from a spontaneous retroperitoneal haematoma. Acute peritonitis has also been described during treatment with the antituberculous agent, isoniazid.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

I. Local response to peritoneal infection:

The first peritoneal response to infection occurs within minutes of bacterial challenge. Bacteria and debris are cleared through the diaphragmatic lacunae into the lymphatic system.

Humoral immune response develops leading to formation of antigen antibody complexes. Degranulation of mast cells and release of histamine causes an increase in vascular permeability. Any noxious stimulus like endotoxin associated with gram negative bacteria, gram positive bacteria, bacteroides species, irritants such as gastric juice, bile salts and meconium probably incite the inflammatory process by inciting mesothelial cell damage or direct activation of the complement system.

Activation of complement leads to production of components C3-a and C5-a, which are powerful chemotactic factors for neutrophils. The initial bactericidal properties of peritoneal fluid are due to activation of the complement cascade. Other cytokines such as interleukin-2 and 8 have been shown to play a key role in recruitment in the cellular defense mechanisms. Within the first 4 to 6 hours, an influx of phagocytic cells into the free peritoneal space occurs that may be associated with a measurable granular cytopenia in the patient's serum.

The omentum also plays a strategic role in the peritoneal cavity's host defense mechanism. Like the stomata of the diaphragm, the omentum has the ability to absorb foreign particles and bacteria. "Milky spots" in the omentum have been described, which are aggregates of polymorphonucleocytes, macrophages and lymphocytes. When stimulated, these milky spots increase in number, develop germinal centers and produce antibodies. The mobility of omentum, allows it to migrate to areas of infection and assist in "walling off" the offending organ.

The inflammatory response that occurs within the peritoneal cavity is characterized by hyperemia, the influx of fluid of ($>500 \text{ cm}^3/\text{hr}$), recruitment of phagocytic cells and fibrin deposition to trap bacteria.

II. Systemic response to peritoneal infection:

After a bacterial challenge, positive blood cultures can be demonstrated in less than 12 minutes. The systemic response to peritoneal infection emulates the response of the body to other forms of injury such as trauma or surgery. The development of hypovolaemia is a phenomenon central to the systemic response and probably results from the fluid influx occurring in the peritoneal cavity.

The subsequent intravascular volume change leads to a reduction in venous return and cardiac output. Systemic hypotension also may be the result of the secretion of TNF, IL-1, platelet activating factor and nitric oxide.^{28,29}

Diminished urine flow develops as a result of the effects of increased aldosterone and anti diuretic hormone secretion, reduced cardiac output and inters renal shunting of blood. This is the setting that has been dubbed as "warm" septic shock, characterized by tachycardia, fever, oliguria, hypotension and warm extremities.

Abdominal distention secondary to accumulated fluid within the peritoneal cavity – creates restriction to diaphragmatic mobility and decreases ventilatory volume, creating eventual atelectasis. The accumulation of fluid in the pulmonary interstitium and alveoli decreases pulmonary compliance and decreased work of breathing. Early manifestation is hyperventilation and the development of respiratory alkalosis. With the worsening of the pulmonary edema and alveolar collapse; severe hypoxemia will develop, creating the adult respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS).

Tissue metabolism is severely altered during the response to peritonitis. Tissue hypoxia leads to anaerobic glycolysis leading to metabolic acidosis. The severe loss in the lean body mass that can occur from protein catabolism occurs rapidly and is only partially ameliorated by the use of nutritional support.

Bacteriology of peritonitis

Peritoneal infection is usually caused by two or more bacterial strains. The commonest are *Escherichia coli*, aerobic and anaerobic streptococci, and the bacteroides. Less frequently *Clostridium welchii* is found; still less frequently *Staphylococci* or *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.⁷

CLINICAL FEATURES AND STAGES³⁰

Peritonitis is an inflammation of the peritoneum either involving a portion or all of the parietal and visceral surfaces of the peritoneal cavity. Perforation of an ulcer into the general peritoneal cavity is a catastrophe that often occurs with dramatic suddenness and unless correctly treated, progresses to the death of the patient. The signs and symptoms produced by the perforation vary according to the time that has elapsed since the rupture occurred. There are three stages in the pathological process that can be recognized. The symptoms of each stage can be enumerated:

Primary stage (within the first two hours)

Also called peritonism or stage of peritoneal irritation and due to sudden outpouring of caustic gastric juice into the peritoneal cavity

- Severe and generalized abdominal pain.
- Anxious countenance.
- Livid or ashen appearance.
- Cold extremities.
- Subnormal temperature (95° F or 96° F).
- Pulse low and weak.
- Shallow respiration.
- Retching or vomiting (slight).
- Pain on top of one or both shoulders.

Second day stage (Two to twelve hours)

Also the stage of peritoneal reaction. The irritant gastric juice is diluted by the peritoneal exudates. Symptoms are reduced but signs are still present.

- Cessation of Vomiting.
- Decreased abdominal pain.
- Normal temperature or slightly elevated temperature.
- Abdominal wall very rigid, tender.
- Tender pelvic peritoneum.
- Diminution of liver dullness.
- Great pain on movement of the body.

Tertiary stage (after twelve hours)

It is the stage of diffuse peritonitis where bacterial peritonitis is established and the patients general condition is worsened.

- Vomiting more frequent but still not profuse.
- Facies of late peritonitis ,classically described as Hippocratic facies
- Abdomen tender and distended.
- Pulse rapid and low; hypovolemic shock may be present.
- Temperature usually elevated.

INVESTIGATIONS

Laboratory Studies:

A complete blood cell (CBC) count with differential count in patients with suspected peritoneal infection. Most patients with intra abdominal infections demonstrate leukocytosis ($> 11,000$ cells / mm³) with a shift to the immature forms on the differential cell count. But patients who are immunocompromised and patients with certain types of infection (e.g. typhoid) may demonstrate absence of leukocytosis and may even demonstrate leucopenia.

Serum amylase and lipase levels in patients with possible diagnosis of pancreatitis. Urine analysis is essential to rule out urinary tract diseases (E.g. pyelonephritis may mimic peritonitis). However patients with lower abdominal and pelvic infection often demonstrate WBC in the urine and microhematuria. The presence of frank pyuria, large number of red blood cells and bacteria in the specimen suggest a urinary source of patient's symptoms.

Widal test

This is a test for the measurement of H and O agglutinins in the patient's sera for typhoid infection. The results are interpreted according to the agglutination titre. The test is taken to be positive if titre is greater than 1/100 for O agglutinin and 1/200 or more for H agglutinin or rise in titre is demonstrated. If positive, ileal perforation should be suspected as the cause of peritonitis.

Peritoneal fluid:

A peritoneal fluid should be evaluated for glucose, protein, and lactate dehydrogenase, and gram stain, aerobic and anaerobic culture. A peritoneal fluid amylase should be done if pancreatitis or pancreatic leak is suspected; creatinine level when a urinary leak is suspected. The peritoneal levels should be compared with serum levels.

Radiographs:³¹

The presence of free, intra abdominal gas almost always indicates perforation of a hollow viscus. The commonest cause is perforation of peptic ulcer; other much less common causes are diverticulitis and malignant tumors. About 70% of perforated ulcers will demonstrate free gas, a phenomenon that is almost never seen in cases of a perforated appendix. As little as 1 ml of free gas can be demonstrated on a radiograph, either an erect chest, or a left lateral decubitus abdominal film. Radiographic techniques are important and the patient should remain in position for 5-10 minutes.

The clinical condition of the patient will determine the radiographic technique used. Chest films taken with the patient in an upright position are ideal for demonstrating free air because the x-ray beam strikes the hemi diaphragms tangentially at their highest point.

A lateral decubitus or even a supine radiograph is used in patients who are too ill to be moved. Left lateral decubitus views of the abdomen are also sensitive for detecting small amount of free air interposed between the free edge of the liver and the lateral wall of the peritoneal cavity. Care should be taken to include the upper abdomen, because air rises to the highest point in the abdomen, which frequently is beneath the lower ribs. Films obtained with the patient in the right lateral decubitus position are also helpful, but gas in the stomach or colon may obscure small amounts

of the free air. Pneumoperitoneum can be detected in 76% of cases using an erect film only, but when a left lateral decubitus projection is included, a pneumoperitoneum can be demonstrated in nearly 90% of cases. Reasons suggested for only 76% perforations manifesting as free gas in peritoneum are sealing of perforation, lack of gas at the site of perforation or adhesions around the site of perforation.

Pseudopneumoperitoneum:³²

A number of conditions have been described which simulate free air in the peritoneal cavity i.e. pseudopneumoperitoneum. These are important because failure to recognize them may lead to an unnecessary laparotomy in search of a perforated viscus.

- Chilaiditi syndrome: is distended bowel, usually hepatic flexure of the colon, Interposed between the liver and the diaphragm.
- Sub diaphragmatic fat
- Curvilinear pulmonary collapse.
- Uneven diaphragm
- Subphrenic abscess.

Pneumoperitoneum without peritonitis:^{32,33}

Occasionally, asymptomatic patients or those with very minimal signs and symptoms are found to have a pneumoperitoneum. Causes of pneumoperitoneum without peritonitis are -

- I. Silent perforation of a viscus which has sealed itself.
- II. Postoperative setting.
- III. Peritoneal dialysis
- IV. Perforated jejunal diverticulosis.
- V. Laparoscopy

Fig 12: X-ray showing gas under the diaphragm.

Use of contrast media in suspected perforation:

Not infrequently, a patient presenting with severe upper abdominal pain has equivocal clinical signs and no free gas is demonstrable on plain radiographs. Water soluble contrast medium (about 50 ml) is given by mouth or injected through a nasogastric tube, with the patient lying on his/her right side. The patient can be examined fluoroscopically or the abdominal radiographs can be repeated after the patient has remained in this position for 5 minutes. Duodenal ulcers which have perforated but show no free gas will normally demonstrate evidence of a leak of contrast medium.

Patients with pancreatitis may have an oedematous stretched duodenal loop. Ionic water soluble contrast medium should not be given if the patient's clinical state is such that there is risk of it being inhaled and causing pulmonary oedema.³²

Ultrasound

Ultrasound examination allows very rapid screening in suspected patients. Visualization of an interference echo with a shifting phenomenon is a very strong indication of the presence of free air in the abdominal cavity. This interference echo can be defined as the interruption of echo transmission due to the space between the parietal peritoneum and the surface of the liver. This free air within the peritoneal cavity can be shifted by changing the patient's position. Since the distal stomach and proximal duodenum are the most frequent sites of peptic ulcer disease, focal peritonitis due to perforation is located in the right upper quadrant. Unlike free peritoneal fluid, this localised exudate doesn't change shape or location when the patient's position is altered. Findings are subphrenic or subhepatic collections.^{32,34,35}

Computed tomography of abdomen

The Computed tomography diagnosis of perforation was based on the direct findings of extraluminal air or gastrograffin. Indirect findings are an abscess or inflammatory mass surrounding an enterolith in the region of appendix or a bowel wall related phlegmon or abscess with fluid in the mesentery or surrounding radiopaque foreign body. Computed tomography is a valuable method in the diagnosis of alimentary tract perforation. The diagnosis can be established rapidly without patient preparation and with a high sensitivity.³⁶

MANAGEMENT OF PATIENT WITH PERITONITIS

The mainstay of success is timely surgical intervention to stop delivery of bacteria and adjuvants into the peritoneal cavity. Management of peritonitis can be broadly divided into supportive and surgical treatment.

Principles of Supportive measures are

- A. To combat hypovolemia and shock
- B. To treat bacteremia, not eliminated by surgery, with antibiotics
- C. To support failing organ systems
- D. To provide adequate nutrition

In all cases of peritonitis, some degree of hypovolemia is present. This is owing to the “third spacing” of extracellular fluid within the peritoneal cavity, which can be sometimes immense. The rate and rapidity at which resuscitation is instituted, depends on the severity and acuity of the condition. If a patient is young and surgically fit and has presented early, the duration of resuscitation, may have to be curtailed in favor of early surgery. In contrast, in elderly patients who present late, the resuscitation takes predominance and surgery may have to be considered after reassessing the patient after resuscitation.

The effectiveness of fluid replacement efforts can be judged by pulse rate, blood pressure and mental status. Monitoring of accurate urine output is essential to find out about adequate resuscitation. Invasive procedures like peripheral arterial and central cardiac pressure monitoring catheters are usually reserved for high risk patients. Supplementary oxygen and positive ventilation may be required in some cases.

Recent studies have shown that institution of IPPV causes decreased incidence of sepsis syndrome by blocking diaphragmatic stomata, thereby preventing flooding of

circulation with bacteria.³⁷ Nasogastric decompression is necessary to reduce abdominal distension and to prevent pulmonary aspiration. Antacid therapy like H2 blockers should be administered to prevent stress gastric ulceration.

Antibiotic therapy

Empiric antibiotic therapy should be initiated, as soon as diagnosis of peritonitis is made. The antibiotic used depend on the presumed bacteria present. E. coli and B.fragilis are the main target organisms for therapy.

Mild to moderate intra-abdominal infection	Severe intra-abdominal infection without renal dysfunction	Severe intra-abdominal infection with renal dysfunction
Second or third generation Cephalosporin Or β -lactamase inhibitor combination or Monobactam + Metronidazole	Carbapenem or Fluroquinolone + Metronidazole Or Aminoglycoside + Metnonidazale +/- Ampicillin	Carbapenem or Fluoroquinolone + Metronidazole

Operative treatment: the principles are^{38,39,40}

Principle 1 (Repair): Control the source of infection

Principle 2 (Purge): Evacuate bacterial inoculum, pus (peritoneal 'toilet')

Principle 3 (Decompress): Treat abdominal compartment syndrome

Principle 4 (Control): Prevent or treat persistent and recurrent infection or verify both

Principle 1

Eliminating the source of infections may include procedures extending from simple perforation closure to major resections. If extensive bowel is gangrenous, exteriorization may be preferred. The perforation can be closed with pedicle or free omental grafts also. The choice of the procedure, and whether the ends of resected

bowel are anastomosed, exteriorized, or simply closed depends on the anatomic source of infection, the degree of peritoneal inflammation and generalized septic response, and the patient's premorbid conditions.

Principle 2

All the infectious peritoneal fluid, pus, should be removed. Necrotic peritoneal tissue should be debrided – an aggressive debridement should be avoided to prevent excessive blood loss or bowel injury. Peritoneal irrigation or lavage should be done thoroughly with adequate amount of normal saline which is warmed. Addition of antibiotic to the solution may be helpful.^{41,42} Experimental studies using rabbit models have shown that addition of antibiotic into the lavage fluid, reduced mortality and incidence of intra abdominal abscess formation.⁴³

Principle 3

During acute peritonitis, the peritoneum and its submesothelial loose connective tissue may absorb more than 10 liters of inflammatory oedema. Draining the peritoneal fluid reduces the abdominal compartment pressure in most cases. However coexistent ileus, visceral and perietal oedema may increase intra abdominal pressure to levels producing compartment syndrome. The closure of abdominal wall with tension will add to this. Laparostomy or staged abdominal repair techniques will obviate the increase in intra abdominal pressure.

Principle 4

Complications that may arise during post operative period should be anticipated by the surgeon. This will result in early diagnosis and re-exploration when indicated. Whenever needed, planned re-laparotomy should be done if surgeon is not convinced of eradication of septic focus. The surgical options have been classified

into the following groups by international society of surgery in its International Surgical Week in Hong Kong.

1. Open abdomen / laparostomy (OPA)
2. Covered laparostomy (COLA)
3. Planned re-laparotomy (PR)
4. Staged abdominal repair (STAR)

The open abdominal techniques (OPA and COLA) avert deleterious effects of increased intraabdominal pressure. OPA includes laparotomy without approximation and suture closure of abdominal fascia and skin.

PERITONEAL LAVAGE IN PERITONITIS

Price first advocated washing the contaminated peritoneal cavity with large volumes of irrigant in 1905⁹. Lavage is done on the basis that phagocytic macrophages and neutrophils cannot function unless attached to peritoneal serosa. They cannot function if they are swimming as phagocytes already dislodged from peritoneum are either dead or non-functional, in which case lavage causes no harm.

There are 3 basis principles of peritoneal lavage:

1. To wash the digestive enzymes, that might have leaked into the peritoneal cavity.
2. To remove material like pus, blood and faeces that could harbor or nourish bacteria.
3. To potentiate the antibiotic effect by allowing the topical application of relatively high dosage of these agents.

Various studies to know the importance of peritoneal lavage and efficacy of different normal saline and different antibiotics have been done.

MECHANISM OF ACTION

The primary role of the surgeon in managing patients with peritonitis is to control the source of contamination. Failure to do so results in septicemia and a universally poor prognosis.⁴⁴ Secondary treatment aims include reducing the bacterial load in the peritoneal cavity by lavage, antibiotics, or both. Lavage is claimed to remove not only bacteria but also material that may promote bacterial proliferation (eg, blood) and proinflammatory cytokines that may enhance local inflammation. The concept of lavaging a contaminated or infected peritoneal cavity makes good sense intuitively. However, because microbes adhere to mesothelial cells, it is very difficult

to wash them off the peritoneal surface. During fecal contamination of the peritoneal cavity, it has been demonstrated that bacteria that adhered to the mesothelium were resistant to intraperitoneal lavage, resulting in only transitory reductions of bacterial populations. Peritoneal irrigation with normal saline is not sufficient to eliminate all fecal contamination produced during the surgical act. With the antibiotic lavage there is topical effect of the antibiotics which could completely inhibit the growth of bacteria in the peritoneum, even when microorganisms have adhered to the mesothelial cells.²

LAVAGE SOLUTIONS

There have been numerous attempts to define an appropriate lavage solution. These attempts have included altering the osmolality and pH and using various antiseptic solutions. Altering the pH of the lavage solution has attracted interest as a therapeutic intervention. This follows from the observation that the pH in an abscess is often acidic. There have been two small clinical reports of patients with intraabdominal abscesses in which the surgeons attempted continuous abdominal lavage with an 8.4% sodium bicarbonate solution in one series⁴⁵ and an acidic solution in the other.⁴⁶ Both series claimed success for their management regime, but the evidence is mainly anecdotal. A variety of antiseptics have been added to lavage solutions in an endeavor to improve their efficacy.

ANTISEPTIC LAVAGE

A variety of antiseptics have been added to lavage solutions in an endeavor to improve their efficacy. Povidone-iodine (betadine) lavage solution has been the most frequently studied. Lavage with povidoneiodine solution has been found to increase mortality. Similarly chlorhexidine lavage and hydrogen peroxide lavage has also been used. But most of studies condemn antiseptic lavage.

ANTIBIOTIC LAVAGE

Since the introduction of antimicrobials to general surgery in the 1940s there has been interest in their topical application in peritonitis⁴⁷. A number of studies have evaluated the efficacy of antibiotic lavage. There were many proponents of lavaging the abdomen with antibiotic solutions in the presence of peritonitis. Scientific evidence indicated that this technique could completely inhibit the growth of bacteria in the lavage solution⁴⁸ but it ignored the effects of the lavage on those bacteria firmly bound to the peritoneum or lodged in fibrin plugs. The antibiotics used have included metranidazole, gentamicin sulfate, cephalothin, lincomycin, kanamycin, doxycycline, and ampicillin.

METRONIDAZOLE LAVAGE

Metronidazole has bactericidal action on *Entamoeba histolytica*, Gram-negative anaerobes like *Bacteroides* and *Fusobacterium* and Gram-positive anaerobes like peptostreptococci and *Clostridia*. It is hypothesized that addition of metronidazole will that the removal of bacteria and their products and improve the time to resolution. . It is also evident that the removal of infection from the peritoneal cavity is more than a simple mechanical task because pathogens become adherent to the peritoneum and then invade the submesothelial tissues. This technique could completely inhibit the growth of bacteria in the lavage solution.

METRONIDAZOLE⁴⁹

PHARMACOLOGY

Mechanism of Action: Inhibits nucleic acid synthesis by disrupting DNA and causing strand breakage; amebicidal, bactericidal, trichomonacidal.

Absorption

Bioavailability: 80% absorption from GI tract

Protein binding : <20

Peak serum time: 1-2 hr

Distribution : Widely distributed; similar pattern for PO and IV

Metabolism : Liver

Enzymes inhibited: Hepatic CYP2C9

Half-life: 25-75 hr (neonates); 8 hr (others); prolonged in patients with hepatic impairment

Excretion: Urine (77%); feces (14%)

DOSING

Loading dose: 15 mg/kg IV; not to exceed 4 g/day

Maintenance dose: 7.5 mg/kg PO/IV (over 1 h) q6hr x 7-10 days \

ANTIMICROBIAL SPECTRUM

Protozoans like *Entamoeba histolytica*, *Giardia lamblia* and *Trichomonas vaginalis*.

Gram-negative anaerobes belonging to the *Bacteroides* and *Fusobacterium*.

Gram-positive anaerobes such as peptostreptococci and *Clostridia*.

ADVERSE EFFECTS

Appetite loss, Candidiasis, Diarrhea, Dizziness, Headache, Nausea, Vomiting, Ataxia,

Dark urine, Disulfiram-type reaction with ethanol, etc.

CONTRAINDICATIONS

Hypersensitivity to metronidazole or other nitroimidazoles, Pregnancy, 1st trimester,

Use of disulfiram within past 2 weeks.

REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES

In a prospective study by Saha SK⁵⁰, the treatment of intraabdominal sepsis with adjuvant metronidazole lavage was carried out at the end of the all operative procedures (including emergency surgery for peritonitis and elective surgeries for a variety of lesions). As a result, there was not a single instance of intraabdominal abscess. The incidence of wound infection was 2.66% in the emergency group and 0% in the elective group; mortality was 5% and 3.9%, respectively. Therefore, author concludes adjuvant metronidazole lavage provides confidence in the treatment of intraperitoneal abscess, and it enhances a quick recovery. It is safe to use and cost effective.

A prospective, randomized study was conducted by Ruiz-Tovar et al² in which patients were divided into 2 groups: Group 1 (intraabdominal irrigation with normal saline) and Group 2 (intraperitoneal irrigation with a solution of 240 mg gentamicin and 600 mg clindamycin). The occurrence of wound infections and intraabdominal abscesses were investigated. After the anastomosis, a microbiologic sample of the peritoneal surface was obtained (sample 1). A second sample was collected after irrigation with normal saline (sample 2). Finally, the peritoneal cavity was irrigated with a gentamicin-clindamycin solution and a third sample was obtained (sample 3). Intra-abdominal abscess rates were 6% in Group 1 and 0% in Group 2. The culture of sample 1 was positive in 68% of the cases, sample 2 was positive in 59%, and sample 3 in 4%. Intraabdominal abscess rates were 6% in Group 1 and 0% in Group 2. Therefore author concludes that Antibiotic lavage of the peritoneum is associated with a lower incidence of intra-abdominal abscesses and wound infections.

A retrospective study was conducted by Parcels et al.⁵¹ In the study all patients, who underwent appendectomies and were irrigated with Normal saline or

Dakin's solution or Imipenem solution, were evaluated in terms of the incidences of postoperative overall Surgical Site infection (SSI), wound infection, and abdominal abscess. A total of 1,063 cases were identified. Saline had an SSI rate of 9.8% ,a wound infection rate of 7.3%, and an abdominal abscess rate of 4.2% . Dakin's had an SSI rate of 20.7%, a wound infection rate of 15.9% , and an abdominal abscess rate of 9.1%. Imipenem irrigation had an SSI rate of 0.5% , a wound infection rate of .5% and an abdominal abscess rate of 0.5%. Thus results suggest that abdominal irrigation with an antibiotic solution (imipenem 1 mg/mL) is superior to both normal saline and Dakin's solution.

In a meta-analysis done by Qadan et al,⁵² a literature search of experimental studies assessing the effect of peritoneal lavage following peritonitis was conducted using Medline, EMBASE and Cochrane databases. The study demonstrated a significant reduction in mortality with antibiotic lavage compared to patients with normal saline lavage. The survival benefit persisted regardless of systemic antibiotic therapy.

In a retrospective study of 189 children with peritonitis, secondary to appendicular perforation, Stewart DJ and Matheson NA⁵³ concluded that antibiotic peritoneal lavage resulted in a significant reduction in the duration of hospital stay. Antibiotic peritoneal lavage also resulted in a significant reduction in the number of children with septic and adhesive complications compared with antiseptic lavage and no lavage, mainly as a result of fewer wound infections and none of the children treated with antibiotic peritoneal lavage required reoperation for intraperitoneal sepsis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Source of data

All patients admitted in B.L.D.E.U.'s Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Bijapur with peritonitis and underwent laparotomy were taken as subjects for study.

2. Method of collection of data

Inclusion criteria

All patients with peritonitis who underwent laparotomy.

Exclusion criteria

Patient younger than 15 years

Patients older than 65 years.

Sample size: Minimum of 38 cases in either group.

The study period is from Oct. 2012 to May 2014.

Procedure

During laparotomy 5ml of contaminated peritoneal fluid is aspirated with syringe (or a pus culture swab is taken) and is sent for culture and sensitivity. The peritoneal cavity is thoroughly washed out with warm normal saline at the end of operative procedure. Metronidazole solution was then added to all areas of abdomen and parietal wound using 20 ml syringe. The dosage was 1 g (200 ml) for all intra abdominal operations. It is not mixed with saline or aspirated back right away. This was done by clamping the drainage tubing, brought out through separate incision, for 2 hours and later clamp was opened.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS:

Peritoneal lavage with normal saline and metronidazole solution is more effective than just plain normal saline lavage and it considerably reduces incidence of intra abdominal abscesses, surgical site infections and hospital stay.

3. SAMPLING:

Sampling Method : Simple random sampling.

Following formula has been used to estimate the sample size for the comparison of normal saline & metronidazole lavage versus plain normal saline lavage.

$$n = \frac{z_{\alpha/2}^2 P Q}{e^2}$$
$$\frac{1.96^2 * 0.9734 * 0.0266}{0.0511624^2}$$
$$= 38$$

e – the permissible error (value of estimator – value of parameter)

$Z_{\alpha/2}$ - be the critical value of z distribution at 5% level of significance.

p - Be the incidences of surgical site infection⁵⁰ ($p = 0.9734$ with reference to the article)

$$q = 1 - p$$

Following statistical tests will be used to compare the results:

1. Students t – test for the valid conclusion about the two groups under study (i.e lavage with saline and metronidazole solution versus plain normal saline.)
2. Mean \pm S.D.
3. P \pm S.E (P)
4. Diagrammatic presentations.

4. Investigations or interventions that will be conducted on patients:

- a) Complete blood count.
- b) Urine – sugar, albumin and microscopy.
- c) Random blood sugar, serum creatinine and serum urea.
- d) Serum C – Reactive protein – If required.
- e) Peritoneal fluid culture and antibiotic sensitivity.
- f) X-Ray Erect Abdomen.
- g) Electro-cardio-gram and Chest X-ray (when age of patient is >35yrs, or if necessary).
- h) Ultrasonography of Abdomen/Pelvis if required.
- i) Computed Axial Tomography of abdomen - if required.

RESULTS

76 Cases of peritonitis who underwent explorative laparotomy were studied. 38 cases received normal saline and metronidazole lavage and 38 cases received plain normal saline lavage.

Table 1 Age Specific Distribution of Cases

Age	Number	Percentage
15-20	9	11.80%
20-30	4	5.20%
30-40	13	17.10%
40-50	14	18.40%
50-60	20	26.30%
60-65	16	21.00%
Total	76	100%

Case studies were in age group from 15 to 65 years. Highest number of cases were seen in age group of 50 to 60 years and 60 to 65 years , 26.30% and 21.00% respectively. Lowest number was in age group of 20 to 30 years, 5.20%.

Graph 1 Age Specific Distribution of Cases

Table 2 Sex Distribution of peritonitis cases

Sex	Number	Percentage
Male	58	76.30%
Female	18	23.60%
Total	76	100%

Majority of cases were males. Male to female ratio – 3.22:1

Graph 2 Sex distributions of cases

TABLE 3 Causes of Peritonitis

Diagnosis	Number of Cases	Percentage
Duodenal Ulcer Perforation	23	30.30%
Intestinal Obstruction	16	21.10%
Appendicular Perforation	10	13.20%
Illeal perforation	9	11.84%
Gastric Perforation	5	6.60%
Colonic Perforation	4	5.26%
Jejunal Perforation	3	3.94%
Primary Peritonitis	2	2.60%
G.B Perforation	2	2.60%
Ruptured Liver Abscess	1	1.30%
Necrotizing pancreatitis	1	1.30%
Total	76	100%

Graph 3 Causes of Peritonitis

Table 4 Operative Procedures Performed

Procedures	Number	Percentage
Primary Closure	34	44.70%
Resection & Anastomosis	26	34.20%
Appendectomy	10	13.20%
Exploratory laparotomy with Lavage	3	3.90%
Open Cholecystectomy	2	2.60%
Necrosectomy	1	1.30%
Total	76	100%

Graph 4 Operative Procedures Performed

Table 5 Outcome in Saline lavage Group

Parameters	Number of cases	Percentage
Wound Infection	11	28.90%
Intra Abdominal abscesses	4	10.50%
Sepsis	13	38.20%
Fecal Fistula	1	2.60%
Death	3	7.90%

In Saline group incidence of wound infection was 28.90%. 10.50 % of patients had intra abdominal abscess. Sepsis was present in 38.20% of patients. 2.60% of patients developed fecal fistula during post operative period. Mortality was 7.90% in this group.

Graph 5 Outcome in Saline Lavage Group

Table 6 Outcome in Metronidazole and Normal saline Lavage group

Parameters	Number of cases	Percentage
Wound Infection	5	13.20%
Intra Abdominal abscesses	2	5.30%
Sepsis	8	21.10%
Fecal Fistula	2	5.30%
Death	4	10.50%

In metronidazole and normal saline lavage group incidence of wound infection was 13.20%. 5.30 % of patients had intra abdominal abscess. Sepsis was present in 21.10% of patients. 5.30% of patients developed fecal fistula during post operative period. Mortality was 10.50% in this group.

Graph 6 Outcome in Metronidazole and Normal saline lavage group

Table 7 Comparison of outcomes of Plain Normal Saline group versus Normal saline and Metronidazole lavage group

Parameter	Saline Lavage Group	Metronidazole Lavage Group	Z Value	P-Value
Wound Infection	28.90%	13.20%	1.71	0.08
Intra Abdominal abscesses	10.50%	5.30%	0.84	0.4
Sepsis	38.20%	21.10%	1.66	0.09
Fecal Fistula	2.60%	5.30%	0.6	0.548
Death	7.9	10.50%	0.39	0.689

There is 15.79 % reduction in incidence of wound infection when Metronidazole is used for IOPL. Incidence of intra abdominal abscess is reduced by 5.26. There is 13.15% reduction in systemic sepsis when Metronidazole is used for IOPL.. There is reduction in total hospital stay by 1.24 days. There is slight increase of 2.6 % in the incidence of post operative fecal fistula when metronidazole is used. There is 2.63% increased in mortality when Metronidazole is used for IOPL. Chi square test did not show any statistical significance of these apparent advantages of metronidazole lavage over saline lavage.

Graph 7 Comparison between Normal Saline and Metronidazole + Normal Saline Lavage group

Table 8 Mean Hospital stay in Normal Saline Lavage group vs Metronidazole and Normal Saline lavage group

Saline Lavage group	Metronidazole lavage group	Difference
13.81 days	12.57 days	1.24 days

Graph 8. Mean Hospital stay in Normal Saline lavage group vs Metronidazole and Normal Saline lavage group

The shortest post operative period was 3 days, where the patient died on third postoperative day. The earliest discharge was 6 days of hospital stay. The longest hospital was 34 days. Mean hospital stay in normal saline lavage was 13.81 days and mean hospital stay in metronidazole group was 12.57 days. There was reduction of 1.24 days in hospital stay which was not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

The treatment of peritonitis is associated with a high morbidity and mortality. The usual treatment of the peritonitis consists of fluid replacement, nasogastric suction, IV antibiotics and operative intervention. Operation consists of suction of the fluid, which has collected in the peritoneal cavity, and definitive procedure for the pathology of the peritonitis (closure of perforation, closure bypass, resection and anastomosis or appendicectomy etc.). This is followed by peritoneal lavage and then the abdomen is closed with drain/drains. 76 patients were included in this study. Patients were randomly assigned into two groups' i.e. Saline lavage group and metronidazole lavage group.

Age

In this study it was found that maximum numbers of cases were in the age group of 50 years to 60 years. Least number of cases were in group 20 years to 30 years age group. Mean age of patients in this study was 44.6 years. In contrast, study done by sheeraz khan et al⁵⁵, maximum number of patients were in age group of 31-40 years. Mean age in this study was 37 years.

Table 9 Comparison of age distribution with previous studies

Age group	Present Study	Deviprasad ⁵⁴ (2011)	Sheeraz Khan et al ⁵⁵ (2009)	Sachin ⁵⁶ (2006)
<20 years	11.80%	2%	21.25%	11%
21-30 years	5.20%	32%	16.25%	23%
31-40 years	17.10%	30%	23.75%	19%
41-50 years	18.40%	23%	18.75%	24%
51-60 years	26.30%	13%	15%	15%
>60 years	21.00%	-	6.6%	8%

Patients younger than 15 years and older than 60 years were excluded in this study.

Sex Distribution

Table 10 Comparison of sex distribution of cases with previous studies

Sex	Present Study	Deviprasad⁵⁴ (2011)	Sheeraz Khan et al⁵⁵ (2009)	Sachin⁵⁶ (2006)
Male	76.30%	86%	78.75%	90%
Female	26.30%	14%	21.25%	10%

There was male preponderance of cases in present study, which is consistent with other studies. Male to female ratio was 3.22:1

CAUSES OF PERITONITIS

Table 11 Comparison of cause of peritonitis

Cause of peritonitis	Present study	Sachin ⁵⁶ (2006)	Deviprasad ⁵⁴ (2011)
Duodenal Ulcer Perforation	30.30%	73%	60%
Intestinal Obstruction with gangrene	21.10%	-	-
Appendicular Perforation	13.20%	-	9%
Ileal perforation	11.84%	8%	21%
Gastric Perforation	6.60%	5%	5%
Colonic Perforation	5.26%	-	-
Jejunal Perforation	3.94%	-	1%
Primary Peritonitis	2.60%	-	-
G.B Perforation	2.60%	-	-
Ruptured Liver Abscess	1.30%	-	-
Infected Necrotizing pancreatitis	1.30%	-	-

Duodenal perforation was the leading cause of peritonitis in present study, followed by gangrenous intestinal obstruction and appendicular perforation and then gastric perforation. Gall bladder perforation, rupture liver abscess and infected necrotizing pancreatitis were less common cause of peritonitis.

Table 12 Comparison of outcome in different studies

Parameter	Present Study		Deviprasad ⁵⁴ (2011)		Schein et al ⁵⁷ (1990)		Sheeraz Khan ⁵⁵ et al (2009)		Parcells et al ⁵¹ (2009)	
	Saline	Metronidazole	Saline	Metronidazole	Saline	Chloram-phenichol	Saline	Superoxide Solution	Daikin Solution	Imipenem
Wound Infection	28.90%	13.20%	40%	26%	17%	17%	72.2%	52%	20.7%	0.5%
Intra Abdominal abscesses	10.50%	5.30%	12%	10%	-	-	-	-	9.1%	0.5%
Sepsis	38.20%	21.10%	28%	18%	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fecal Fistula	2.60%	5.30%	6%	6%	-	-	5%	2.5%	-	-
Death	7.9	10.50%	8%	10%	21%	10%	5%	5%	-	-

Wound Infection

There is 15.79 % reduction in incidence of wound infection when Metronidazole is used for IOPL. However this is statistically not significant (P= 0.08). Deviprasad⁵⁴ reported reduction of 14 % in wound infection when metronidazole lavage was given. Similarly *Sheeraz khan et al*⁵⁵ reported 20% reduction in incidence of wound infection, when superoxide solution was used. *Parcells et al*⁵¹ reported very significant reduction in wound infection when Imipenem solution was used for lavage. On contrary, *Schein et al*⁵⁷ did not find any difference in incidence of wound infection when cholarmphemicol was used for lavage.

Intra abdominal abscess

There is 5.26 % reduction in incidence of wound infection when Metronidazole is used for IOPL. However this is statistically not significant (P= 0.4). Deviprasad⁵⁴ reported reduction of 2 % when metronidazole lavage was given. *Parcells et al*⁵¹ reported very significant reduction in intraabdominal abscess from 9.1% to 0.5 % when Imipenem solution was used for lavage.

Sepsis

There is 17.1% reduction in systemic sepsis when Metronidazole is used for IOPL. But this is statistically not significant (P = 0.09) where as Deviprasad⁵⁴ reported reduction of 10 %.

Fecal Fistula

Present study did not find any significant difference in the incidence of postoperative fecal fistula in each group. Contrarily there was increase in incidence of fecal fistula by 2.6% in metronidazole IOPL group, but this increase was not found to be significant (P=0.548) .

Mortality

In present study there is 2.63% increase in mortality when Metronidazole is used for IOPL. But it is not statistically significant (P = 0.689). *Schein et al*⁵⁷ found no significant difference in mortality of patients treated with cholarmphemicol.

Post operative hospital stay

In present study Mean hospital stay in normal saline lavage was 13.81 days and mean hospital stay in metronidazole group was 12.57 days. There was reduction of 1.24 days in hospital stay which was not statistically significant. *Sheeraz khan et al*⁵⁵ reported reduction in hospital stay by 1.5 days in superoxide group.

CONCLUSION

- Peritonitis is most common in the age group of 50 to 60 yrs (26%).
- There is a male preponderance with Male: Female ratio of 3.22:1
- Duodenal ulcer perforation (30.3%) is the most common cause of peritonitis, followed by obstruction (16%) , appendicular (13.2%), and so on.
- Primary closure of the perforation with Graham's patch repair is the most commonly performed operation (44.7%) followed by resection and anastomosis (34.2%), appendicectomy (13.2%).
- There is 15.79 % reduction in incidence of wound infection when Metronidazole is used for IOPL. But this is statistically not significant.
- Incidence of intra abdominal abscess is reduced by 5.26% in Metronidazole lavage group, which is statistically not significant.
- There is 17.1% reduction in systemic sepsis when Metronidazole is used for IOPL.
- There is reduction in total hospital stay by 1.24 days.
- There is a slight increase by 2.6 % in the incidence of post operative fecal fistula and mortality when metronidazole is use which could be attributed to selection bias but it's not statistically significant.
- Addition of metronidazole to normal saline for intraoperative peritoneal lavage has beneficial effect in terms of reduction in incidence of wound infection, intraabdominal abscess, systemic sepsis and postoperative hospital stay. However these are not statistically significant.
- Further studies with larger sample size are needed to accurately assess the statistical significance of beneficial role of metronidazole lavage in operated cases of peritonitis.

SUMMARY

The study was done on 76 patients presenting with features of peritonitis and eventually getting operated at BLDEU'S Shri B.M. Patil Medical College & Research Center. Patients were randomly divided into two groups i.e. Plain Normal Saline Lavage group and Metronidazole with Normal saline lavage group.

Duodenal ulcer perforation was the most common cause of peritonitis and primary closure of perforation with graham's patch was most commonly performed procedure. Male patients were 3.22 times more common than female patients.

There was reduction in incidences of wound infection, sepsis, intra abdominal abscess and mean hospital stay in metronidazole lavage group as compare to saline lavage group, but not upto significant levels. However there was increase in mortality and fecal fistula by 2.6% in metronidazole lavage group which could be attributed to selection bias and was also statistically not significant. Larger studies are needed to assess the statistical significance of these findings.

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ANNEXURE I

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR-586 103
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this college met on 18-10-2012 at 3-30 pm to scrutinize the Synopsis of Postgraduate Students of this college from Ethical Clearance point of view. After scrutiny the following original/corrected & revised version synopsis of the Thesis has been accorded Ethical Clearance.

Title "A Comparative Study of intra operative peritoneal lavage with normal saline & metronidazole Solution versus plain normal saline in cases of peritonitis"

Name of P.G. student Dr. Rakshit Aggarwal
Surgery

Name of Guide/Co-investigator Dr. S.N. Khairatkar
Assoc prof of Surgery

DR. TEJASWINI VALLABHA
CHAIRMAN
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE
BLDEU'S, SHRI.B.M.PATIL
MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR.

Following documents were placed before E.C. for Scrutinization

- 1) Copy of Synopsis/Research project.
- 2) Copy of informed consent form
- 3) Any other relevant documents.

ANNEXURE II

CLINICAL PHOTOGRAPHS

FIG. 1 GANGRENOUS SMALL BOWEL

FIG. 2 DUODENAL ULCER PERFORATION

FIG. 3 ILLEAL PERFORATION

FIG. 4 LARGE BOWEL OBSTRUCTION

FIG. 5 DUODENAL ULCER PRIMARY CLOSURE WITH GRAHAM'S PATCH

FIG 6. RESECTION AND ANASTOMOSIS OF SMALL BOWEL

ANNEXURE III

SAMPLE INFORMED CONSENT FORM

B.L.D.E.U.'s SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL
AND RESEARCH CENTER, BIJAPUR – 586103, KARNATAKA

TITLE OF THE PROJECT—

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF
INTRA OPERATIVE PERITONEAL
LAVAGE WITH NORMAL SALINE
& METRONIDAZOLE SOLUTION
VERSUS PLAIN NORMAL SALINE
IN CASES OF PERITONITIS.**

P.G. GUIDE —

**Dr. Hemanth Kumar M
M.S General Surgery,
Assoc. Prof. of General Surgery
Ph-no. (08352) 262770**

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR —

**Dr. Rakshit Aggarwal
Dept. of General Surgery
Ph-no. (08352) 262770**

Purpose of research:-

I have been explained about the reason for doing this study and selecting me/my ward as a subject for this study. I have also been given free choice for either being included or not in the study.

This study is to evaluate whether intra operative normal saline and metronidazole solution lavage is better as compared to plain normal saline lavage in

cases of peritonitis in terms of post operative complications, intra abdominal abscess and duration hospital stay.

Procedure:-

I have been explained that depending upon the group allocated to me, during laparotomy I'll be getting either normal saline and metronidazole solution lavage or plain normal saline lavage intra operatively and that beforehand I'll be subjected to certain routine blood and urine investigations and chest x-ray and USG Abdomen, if needed.

Risks and discomforts:-

I understand that I may experience some pain or discomfort while examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment. I understand that appropriate treatment will be given to me depending on the need.

Benefits:-

I understand that my/my wards participation in this study will help to analyze whether normal saline and metronidazole solution lavage given intraoperatively is better than plain saline lavage in terms of post operative complications, sepsis and hospital stay.

Confidentiality:-

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of hospital records and will be subject to confidentiality. Information of sensitive personal nature will not be part of medical record, but will be stored in the investigation research file.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose no name will be used and other identifications such as photographs will be only with special written permission. I understand that I may see the photograph before giving permission.

Request for more information:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time, Dr. Rakshit Aggarwal at the department of surgery is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

Refusal for withdrawal of participation:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice. I also understand that Dr. Rakshit Aggarwal may terminate my participation in the study after he has explained the reasons for doing so.

Injury statement:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me. But, no further compensation would be provided by the hospital. I understand that by my agreements to participate in this study and not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of research, the procedures required and the possible risks to the best of my ability.

Dr. Rakshit Aggarwal

Dr. Hemanth Kumar M

Date

Study subject consent statement:

I confirm that Dr. Rakshit Aggarwal has explained to me the purpose of research, the study procedure, that I will undergo and the possible discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my own language. I have been explained all the above in detail in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore I agree to give consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

(Participant)

Date

(Witness to signature)

Date

ANNEXURE IV

B.L.D.E.U.'s SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL

AND RESEARCH CENTER, BIJAPUR – 586103, KARNATAKA

Pts.Name _____

Age _____ Sex _____ I.P. No. _____

Diagnosis _____

DOA _____ Pt. Code _____

Surgery done _____

DOD _____

Intra-operative Findings _____

CHIEF COMPLAINTS:

HISTORY OF PRESENTING ILLNESS:

PAST HISTORY:

- Diabetes mellitus
- Hypertension
- History of any drug intake
- Renal disease
- Jaundice

FAMILY HISTORY:

GENERAL

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

Build:	Poor / Moderate /Well
Nourishment:	Poor / Moderate / Well
Pallor:	present/absent
Icterus:	present/absent
Clubbing:	present/absent
Generalized Lymphadenopathy:	present/absent

VITALS

PR:	Temp:
BP:	Weight:
RR:	

OTHER SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION:

- Per Abdomen examination
 - Inspection
 - Palpation
 - Percussion
 - Ausculation
- Respiratory System
- Cardiovascular System
- Central Nervous System

INVESTIGATION:

BLOOD: Hb

URINE: Albumin

TC

Sugar

DC

Microscopy

ESR

BT, CT

Blood Urea,

Serum Creatinine

C-reactive protein

Peritoneal fluid culture and sensitivity

RBS

X-Ray Abdomen - Standing

USG Abdomen

CT

Abdomen

		PRE-OP	POD-1	POD-2	POD-3	POD-4	POD-5	POD-6	POD-7	POD-8	POD-9	POD-10
PULSE RATE (/min)												
BLOOD PRESS. (mm Hg)												
TEMPERATURE												
RESP. SYSTEM												
P/A – (Localised tenderness)												
DRAIN	PERF ⁿ . SITE (ml)											
	PEXPLOATIVE LAPAROTOMYVIC (ml)											
INCISION SITE	LEAK/DISCHARGE											
	DEHISCENCE											
	INFECTION											
FLATUS / STOOLS												
W.B.C. COUNT												
ANY OTHER COMPLAINTS												
REMARKS, IF ANY												

KEY TO MASTERCHART

S. No.	Serial Number
IP	In Patient
DOA	Date of admission
DOS	Date of Surgery
DOD	Date of Discharge
M	Metronidazole and Normal Saline lavage
S	Normal Saline Lavage

ANNEXURE-V

MASTER CHART

S. No.	Name	Age	Sex	IP No.	Diagnosis	Surgical procedure	DOA	DOS	DOD	Hospital Stay	Lavage	Wound Infection	Intra abdominal abscess	Sepsis	Fecal Fistula	Death
1	Chandrakant	60	M	27550	Ruptured liver abscess	Explorative Laparotomy with lavage	28.11.12	30.11.12	27.12.12	30	M	x		x		
2	Maruthi	58	M	25334	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	6.11.12	6.11.12	10.12.12	34	S	x		x	x	
3	Kadappa	45	M	23780	Gall bladder perforation	Cholecystectomy	19.10.12	05.11.12	15.11.12	26	S	x		x		Death
4	Maruthi	60	M	25386	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	16.11.12	16.11.12	10.12.12	24	S	x	x	x		
5	Ramappa	60	M	20061	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	07.09.12	07.09.12	17.09.12	10	M					
6	Siddappa	60	M	25780	Gastric perforation	Primary closure	11.11.12	11.11.12	23.11.12	13	S			x		
7	Shivappa	28	M	25051	Necrotizing pancreatitis	Necrosectomy	03.11.12	04.11.12	09.11.12	7	M					
8	Laxmibai	55	M	18583	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	21.08.12	21.08.12	04.09.12	15	S	x		x		
9	Pandu Pawan	58	M	24339	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	26.10.12	26.10.12	09.11.12	15	M					
10	Laxmibai	38	F	22732	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	8.10.12	8.10.12	10.10.12	3	M			x		death
11	Gowarramma	40	F	20493	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	11.09.12	11.09.12	25.09.12	15	S					
12	Basappa	33	M	26176	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	16.11.12	16.11.12	29.11.12	14	S					
13	Laxmibai	55	F	27765	Ileal perforation	Primary closure	30.11.12	4.12.12	09.12.12	10	M			x		death
14	Kashiray	54	M	18866	Gall bladder perforation	Cholecystectomy	24.8.12	29.08.12	10.09.12	16	M	x				
15	Kallappa	55	M	18503	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	21.8.12	21.8.12	1.09.12	10	S					
16	Kallappa	50	M	29838	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	12.12.12	12.12.12	15.12.12	3	M			x		death
17	Shrishail	22	M	30422	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	26.12.12	26.12.12	01.01.13	6	S					
18	Rohan	14	M	19070	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	27.08.12	27.08.12	31.08.12	6	S					
19	Ramappa	32	M	20061	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	07.09.12	07.09.12	17.09.12	10	M					
20	Laxmibai	65	F	22732	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	09.10.12	09.10.12	21.10.12	12	M					
21	Pandu Pawan	58	M	24339	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	26.10.12	26.10.12	06.11.12	10	S	x				
22	Ningamma	58	F	24706	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	30.10.12	30.10.12	07.10.12	8	M					
23	Sanganna	38	M	25158	Blunt trauma abdomen with illeal perforation	Primary closure	05.11.12	05.11.12	29.11.12	24	S	x	x	x		
24	Santosh	40	M	25154	Blunt trauma abdomen with caecal perforation	Resection & anastomosis	06.11.12	06.11.12	17.11.12	11	M					
25	Maruthi	17	M	25334	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	06.11.12	06.11.12	21.11.12	15	S					
26	Gurubasav	28	M	25261	Gastric perforation	Primary closure	09.11.12	09.11.12	21.11.12	12	S					
27	mallapa	64	M	25544	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	09.11.12	09.11.12	07.12.12	29	M	x		x	x	

28	Prashant	12	M	25736	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	11.11.12	11.11.12	17.11.12	6	M				
29	Siddappa	60	M	25780	Ileal perforation	Primary closure	11.11.12	11.11.12	23.11.12	12	M				
30	Basappa	60	M	26176	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	16.11.12	16.11.12	30.11.12	14	S				
31	Amanthinga	18	M	26442	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	19.11.12	19.11.12	30.11.12	11	M				
32	Shekh ahmed	19	M	26201	Gastric perforation	Primary closure	20.11.12	20.11.12	07.12.12	17	S	x		x	
33	Chandrakant	64	M	27550	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	30.11.12	30.11.12	20.12.12	20	S	x		x	
34	Mahalakshmi	36	F	27796	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	30.11.12	30.11.12	18.12.12	18	M				
35	Moulali	30	M	3262	Colonic perforation (ca colon)	Resection & anastomosis	27.02.13	27.02.13	10.02.13	11	M				
36	Rudrappa	62	M	54	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	02.01.13	02.01.13	14.01.13	12	M				
37	Shreekant	35	M	465	Multiple illeal perforations	Resection & anastomosis	06.01.13	06.01.13	20.01.13	14	S				
38	Indramma	50	F	768	Jejunal perforation	Resection & anastomosis	10.01.13	10.01.13	19.01.13	9	S				
39	Dayanand	33	M	1007	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	16.01.13	16.01.13	01.02.13	16	M				
40	Honappa	50	M	1337	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	19.01.13	19.01.13	29.01.13	10	M				
41	Shivanand	48	M	1468	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	21.01.13	21.01.13	09.02.13	18	S	x			
42	Somu Rathod	65	M	1772	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	24.01.13	24.01.13	06.02.13	12	S				
43	Choudamma	65	F	1866	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	25.01.13	25.01.15	19.02.13	24	M	x	x	x	
44	Prabhugouda	55	M	2429	Blunt trauma abdomen with jejunal perforation	Primary closure	02.02.13	02.02.13	06.03.13	33	M	x	x	x	
45	Irramma	48	F	2520	Primary peritonitis	Explorative Laparotomy with lavage	04.02.13	04.02.13	22.02.13	18	S		x	x	
46	Meghappa	45	M	252359	Multiple ileal perforations	Resection & anastomosis	07.02.13	07.02.13	19.02.13	12	M				
47	Basangouda	55	M	3336	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	17.02.13	17.02.13	28.02.13	11	S				
48	Chanbassapa	48	M	3934	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	20.02.13	20.02.13	27.02.13	7	M				
49	Naggappa	50	M	3958	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	20.02.13	20.02.13	01.03.13	9	S				
50	Suresh Rajput	36	M	4005	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	22.02.13	22.02.13	02.03.13	10	S				
51	Karshiri	30	F	4296	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	25.02.13	25.02.13	01.03.13	7	S				
52	Gopal	65	M	5661	Ileal perforation	Primary closure	28.02.13	28.02.13	10.03.13	11	S				
53	Shridevi	18	F	5794	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	03.03.13	03.03.13	10.03.13	7	S				
54	Savita	45	F	5914	Blunt trauma abdomen with caecal perforation	Resection & anastomosis	03.03.13	03.03.13	24.03.13	21	S		x	x	
55	Bhimray	45	M	6603	Gastric perforation	Primary closure	09.03.13	09.03.13	21.03.13	12	M				
56	Baswaraj	19	M	7751	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	19.03.13	19.03.13	25.03.13	6	M				
57	Bandesaab	48	M	7749	Colonic perforation (ca colon)	Resection & anastomosis	23.03.13	23.03.13	27.03.13	4	S			x	death
58	Gundappa	40	M	1768	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	20.01.14	20.01.14	02.02.14	12	S				
59	Veeresh	49	M	2503	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	26.01.14	26.01.14	05.02.14	10	S				

60	Prabhakar	38	M	2805	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	29.01.14	29.01.14	11.02.14	12	M					
61	Hanamawwa	52	M	2829	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	30.01.14	30.01.14	25.02.14	26	M			x	x	
62	Kurtarappa	60	M	3156	Jejunal perforation	Primary closure	01.02.14	01.02.14	15.02.14	14	M					
63	Hanumanth	53	M	3448	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	05.02.14	05.02.14	21.02.14	16	S			x		
64	Balabai	51	M	3705	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	07.02.14	07.02.14	16.02.14	9	S					
65	Vijaya	15	F	4474	Appendicular perforation	Appendectomy	14.02.14	14.02.14	21.02.14	7	M					
66	Muttawwa	63	F	4464	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	15.02.14	15.02.14	24.02.14	9	S					
67	Mareppa	50	M	4944	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	21.02.14	21.02.14	02.03.14	9	M					
68	Ningappa	55	M	5054	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	21.02.14	21.02.14	04.03.14	12	M					
69	Mahesh	40	M	5099	Intestinal obstruction with gangrene	Resection & anastomosis	28.02.14	28.02.14	12.03.14	12	M					
70	Niggapa	21	M	5803	Primary peritonitis	Explorative Laparotomy with lavage	12.03.14	12.03.14	22.03.14	10	M					
71	Jayawwa	58	F	7062	Ileal perforation	Primary closure	15.03.14	15.03.14	27.03.14	12	S	x				
72	Saraswati	30	F	7210	Gastric perforation	Primary closure	14.03.14	14.03.14	17.03.14	3	M					Death
73	Pavana	60	M	7246	Ileal perforation	Resection & anastomosis	17.03.14	17.03.14	07.04.14	20	S	x		x		Death
74	Manoj	18	M	7477	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	19.03.14	19.03.14	29.03.14	10	M					
75	Jarabai	48	F	7730	Duodenal ulcer perforation	Primary closure	19.03.14	19.03.14	28.03.14	9	M					
76	Vidya	30	F	8984	Ileal perforation	Primary closure	31.03.14	31.03.14	11.04.14	11	S					